

HUMOROUS DIALOGIC DISCOURSE AS ONE OF THE MAIN TYPES OF DISCOURSE AND ITS MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. *This article discusses various approaches to the study of discourse, defines the basic unit of dialogic discourse as a statement, and humorous dialogic discourse is considered one of the main types of discourse.*

Keywords: *dialogue, discourse, humor, dialogic discourse, humorous discourse, joke.*

It should be noted that the concept of "dialogue" almost inextricably coexists with the concept of "discourse". The concept of "dialogue" and the issues of intertextual interaction occupied the minds of many researchers.

Having chosen a joke as the subject of research of its discursive textual characteristics, we consider it expedient to give definitions of the concepts of "humorous discourse" and "joke" in modern linguistics, to consider a joke as a genre of humorous dialogical discourse, to identify the actual linguistic and extralinguistic features of a joke as a genre of humorous dialogical discourse and to draw a conclusion about the difference between the type of discourse under study from others with further consideration of the most significant of the identified aspects in the analysis of the joke.

From the above, it becomes clear that discourse is considered as communication, and communication is a conversation, a conversation, a dialogue in which at least two individuals are present: the producer (author, addressee) – the one who speaks, and the recipient (addressee). If the addressee and the addressee exchange replicas, a dialogue is formed.

In ordinary, a dialogue is a conversation between two persons, assuming that "dia" is "two", and "log" is to speak, that is, "when two speak", contrasting this understanding with a monologue when one speaks. But this is a misconception since "dia" in ancient Greek means: separation, separation (Rus. times-); full performance of the action, the full degree of quality (completely, completely); reciprocity of action, competitiveness (rus. re-, against each other); movement from beginning to end (though, through, between). There we also find the interpretation of the concept of "dialogue" – "the exchange of words between interlocutors, that is, there may be three or more interlocutors"[Ibid.]. For example, L. L. Fedorova understands dialogue as "a linguistic form of verbal interaction between two or more participants" [Fedorova 2007]. Linguist B. Y. Norman, following L. P. Yakubinsky, says that the dialogue "is based on the connection between replicas" [Norman 2016, p. 70]; the monologue, according to L. P. Yakubinsky, "represents a certain compositional complexity" [Yakubinsky 1986, p. 36].

The communicative unit of dialogic discourse is a replica of the utterance since it is the utterance that represents the smallest structural unit of two-way speech communication" [Babayan 2020, p. 23]. In addition, in any dialogue, including in an anecdote, there may be a third party – a listener who is silent and does not seem to participate in the conversation, the so-called "silent observer" [Babayan 2010, p. 90; Babayan 2008, p. 85-90].

It is not easy to explain humor, not to mention its definition – in many cases humor and laughter are used as synonyms, which makes it difficult to focus on this phenomenon. In addition, humor and wit are distinguished, since it is spontaneous humor, the ability to make a joke at the right time and in the right place, as a rule, without using jokes; not spontaneous humor is humor prepared in advance: someone somewhere heard or read an anecdote, remembered it, perhaps even as–then transformed and told in suitable situations. According to M. A. Kulinich, humor is "a special way of understanding individual fragments of reality, a unique indicator of people's maturity" [Kulinich 1999, p. 8]. Russian linguist V. I. Karasik believes that humor is an individual's ability to perceive the funny sides of life and considers

this ability as a fundamental characteristic of a person [Karasik 1997, pp. 144-153]. Canadian writer Stephen Leacock, who wrote humorous stories, defines humor as a good-natured attitude to various life inconsistencies and indirect expression of this relationship through art.

According to M. Xu, humorous discourse is a kind of discourse, which by definition is "frivolous" and requires the use of the comic [Xu 2019, p. 44]. It should be noted that humorous discourse cannot be considered institutional, since it is "a text immersed in a situation of laughing communication" [Lavrova 2012, p. 90]. The type of discourse under study – humorous – is distracted from social relations, thanks to it there is a kind of destruction of the social distance between the communicating, ignoring the social hierarchy. Myself, a significant feature that distinguishes humorous discourse from institutional discourse is, according to V. I. Karasik, "overturning established stereotypes of perception and behavior" [Karasik 2002, p. 175]. Institutional discourses are designed to maintain social stereotypes, while humorous discourse destroys any social stereotypes, using laughter to equalize people of different social statuses and different levels of well-being. There are also certain differences at the language level: the institutional discourse is characterized by stereotypical linguistic means, models, and cliches; humorous discourse – original, authors, occasional, language experiments, including language games. Definitions of humorous discourse correlate with definitions of discourse, therefore, the discourse–text relationship can be brought to the fore in the description of the term: "Humorous discourse is a text immersed in a situation of laughing communication" [Karasik 2002, p. 397]. The situation of laughing communication from the point of view of communication, according to V. I. Karasik, is characterized by such signs as the intention of the participants to avoid a serious conversation, to give the humorous tone of communication, the presence of established models of laughing behavior accepted in this linguoculture [Karasik 2002, p. 252]. Other researchers define discourse as speech: "Humorous discourse is an integral form of speech characterized by a frivolous tone of communication, a playful rethinking of current concepts and stereotypes and pursuing an entertaining goal" [Bochkareva

2013, p. 249]. Yu. Yu. Bochkareva also characterizes humorous discourse as a "sphere of game communication" [Ibid., p. 249], in which it is of great importance the author's creativity, and occasional game elements. T. A. Gridina in her works considers the associative strategy of language play as a form of linguocreative activity [Gridina 2008, 2018]. According to N. A. Lavrova, the game is "an integral part of people's activities, including speech activity and speech behavior" [Lavrova 2010, p. 161], that is, the game is one of the most important components of discursive activity. Humorous discourse is related to the game, so it is considered one of the types of discourse that are most in demand by a person. Humorous discourse organically fits into human activity at all stages of the development of society. If we analyze the discursive system of any language, it becomes clear that humorous discourse is a component of game discourse, its other elements include parody and entertainment discourses [Karasik 2014, pp. 248-265; Vorkachev 2016, p. 26]. The organization of communication within the framework of humorous discourse is not an easy task. Humor is often on the verge of a foul, humor in general, and anecdote in particular, has quite provocative in nature, therefore, communication within the framework of humorous discourse may offend the recipient (addressee). However, such an insult in humorous communication should be avoided [Knyazyan 2015].

S. G. Vorkachev draws attention to such an important property of humorous discourse as intellectuality. According to the scientist, the game, on the one hand, requires the use of formed cognitive abilities, and on the other hand, contributes to their formation. The narrator, the humorist does not just "poison" jokes, with his stories he seeks to "cause surprise and admiration in the recipients of speech" [Vorkachev 2016, p. 28], and this is impossible without a certain intellectual component. Intellectuality is considered an important component of such a personal quality, as a sense of humor (wit) relates "to the superstructure categories of homo sapiens as the highest social representative of the terrestrial fauna" [Naumov 2017, p. 100]. In dialogical communication associated with the interweaving of an anecdote into discourse, it is necessary that not only the sender of the message (the

narrator of the joke, the addressee) has a good sense of humor, but also the recipient (the listener of the joke, the addressee) must have no less sense of humor, otherwise communication will not be successful. Some researchers even consider a sense of humor as an integral part of emotional intelligence [Gorbunov 2015]. The works of humorous discourse have substantial and formal (linguistic) components. Exploring the forms of humorous utterance, the most significant can be considered those means of language that the speaker (addressee) uses to represent the humorous meaning.

Among the most famous German researchers of humor should be named Helga Kotthoff, who has devoted many articles to an anecdote, ways of creating a comic, and dialogue in an anecdote. Helga Kotthoff explored various aspects of humor, analyzing, in particular, conversational humor, dealing with the intertextuality of an anecdote, and, in addition, trying to determine the gender characteristics of humor [Kotthoff 2003]. Another famous linguist Ulrich [Ulrich 2014], among other things, he considers wordplay as a means of humor, pointing out that it is possible to achieve a comic effect either by violating the norms of word formation or by using the idiomatic meaning used, as well as through polysemy and homonymy. The researcher emphasizes that language can be used creatively and in the field of humor, intentionally violating the language system and its rules, and norms.

Researchers identify a number of characteristics inherent in the humorous dialogic discourse: the presence of stylistically colored and evaluative vocabulary, an abundance of slang and slang expressions; friendly (unfriendly) nature of the relationship between communicants; conversational formulas of speech, situations of informal treatment, the absence of indicators of subordination, which allows dialogue partners to touch on personal topics in conversation. Since dialogical jokes combine two characteristics – dialogic and humor and the joke refers to the humorous dialogical jokes representing the genre of humorous dialogical discourse. In addition to the above, linguistic techniques are actively used in dialogic communication to create a comic effect, these techniques include comparisons, puns, metaphors, onomatopoeia, repetitions, neologisms, jargon, etc. For humorous dialogic discourse, an unexpected, paradoxical ending of the dialogue is

characteristic, which stimulates laughter; the presence of syntactically simple, short sentences and commonly used words, typical for colloquial speech [Proskurina 2004, pp. 8-10].

Humorous discourse in a joke mostly represents a dialogic type of discourse, which is the subject of this study, that is, humorous dialogic discourse, its features, and specific aspects inherent only in this type of discourse.

In our opinion, the main specific characteristics of a joke within the framework of a humorous dialogic discourse are the following:

- 1) obligatory presence of at least two participants in the communication process – the narrator (addressee) and the recipient (addressee);
- 2) the interaction of the narrator (addressee) and the recipient (addressee) occurs not only verbally, but also nonverbally (the task of the narrator is to make the recipient laugh, to make the recipient smile, and he monitors the reaction of his interlocutor (or the audience in which the joke is told);
- 3) a joke in dialogical form is fully pronounced by the narrator, during the entire time of the anecdote playback, the recipient is only a listener, a kind of "dialogue in dialogue" is formed when another dialogue is indirectly introduced into the communication of two or more participants;
- 4) communication between participants (the narrator and the recipient) is direct and interpersonal; as a rule, jokes are told at a personal meeting, in a lecture hall, at political negotiations, etc.

The humorous discourse of the anecdote text forms an open system, while the coherence of the humorous narrative in it is provided by such implicit means as ellipsis, implication, presupposition, and allusion. The framework of the anecdote text consists of paradigmatic and syntagmatic lines, along them there are structural and thematic types of anecdote. Thematic layers in this system are series and cycles of jokes [Tyukina 2021e, pp. 212-213].

Every good joke violates the expectations of the listener (addressee). If at the beginning of the narration of an anecdote the thoughts of the listener (addressee) move in one direction, then a good anecdote dramatically changes this direction of

thoughts. The element of surprise or the principle of deceived expectation is the basis of any good joke.

Thus, we come to the conclusion that humorous dialogic discourse – joke – as one of the main types of discourse has its own specific linguistic, semantic, pragmatic, and socio-cultural features. A joke creates a situation of laughing communication, it combines an outwardly funny interpretation with an inner seriousness, and has a mostly positive character, since it sublimates aggression and weakens many interpersonal conflicts.

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